

Rational Behavioral Aspects of Entrepreneurs

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ABSTRACT

The present study discusses about the initiatives taken by the Entrepreneurs and the challenges they face in the beginning of their Entrepreneurial journey. Past researches had been done to give clarity to the topic “Entrepreneurship”, they primarily focused on economic factors influencing entrepreneurship. This paper examines what an entrepreneur goes through during the initial phases. How he/ she utilize the opportunities and overcome these challenges. For a better understanding, we interviewed four entrepreneurs running start-ups- Pritam Nanda (Enlve Solutions), Rahul Kanuganti (Flytta Innovations), Badri Narayan Samal (Midday entertainment and media) and Deepak Kumar Nath(Global Tech Promotion) gave insights about the initiatives they took and the challenges they faced during their period of establishment. This paper discusses the views given by today’s entrepreneurs regarding the challenges they faced at the time of starting their own organization. It suggests that Entrepreneurship has a lot of scope in India and with external support, entrepreneurs can enhance in this field for future developmental initiatives.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Start-up initiatives, Entrepreneurial challenges

INTRODUCTION

Startup can be defined as a newly established business. The person should go for a startup only if he is mentally prepared to face challenges. It is an extremely competitive arena. Before starting up a business an entrepreneur must focus on many things like the economic condition of the country he lives in, market conditions, target groups, opportunities, Government support, and competitors (Gans, 2000). A successful entrepreneur is motivated by the idea to bring about a positive and well-intended change to society. They are usually highly focused individuals who have a crystal-clear vision and they are willing to put all the efforts towards their journey to success. An entrepreneur is always in the lookout for fresh avenues and latest technologies to stay ahead in the competition (Wadhwa, 2009). Starting up a business does not mean that the entrepreneur is going to be benefited. It aims at serving the society and improving the economic condition of the country. Successful Startups always have successful innovators from whom a lot can be learnt. All you need is to find the right one. A lot of successful entrepreneurs never thought they would make it this big in life. Let us take a leaf out of the life of Face book founder Mark Zuckerberg. He started a social network for the University he studied and hoped that eventually, someone would make a similar network for the whole world. One thing led to another and finally, he was the person who developed a dorm room project into a 300 billion-dollar corporation.

An entrepreneur must go through turbulent times when starting up. They must face acute peer and family pressure to settle for a “normal” life and settle for a job. Initially, a lot of people are not able to understand the vision they see towards an improved world. On top of that, there is a lack of motivation and self-doubt that sometimes make the life of an entrepreneur

full of struggles and hardships (Lockett, 2013). Thus, goes the famous saying- “Entrepreneurship is a lonely journey”. Steve Jobs has a famous saying about the power of perseverance. He said, “Half of what separates the successful entrepreneurs from the unsuccessful ones is pure perseverance”. It takes a lot of patience and mental strength to work towards a vision that not many understand. This theory is further strengthened by the words of Twitter founder and CEO Biz Stone. He said, “Timing, perseverance, and ten years of trying will eventually make you look like an overnight success”. However, it is a sad reality that not everyone can sustain in an ecosystem that is filled with uncertainty and doubt. People are often weighed by other responsibilities and fail to find success in the space. An entrepreneur takes the journey as an adventurous voyage that is filled with turbulence and success in equal measure. “It’s a sweet-sour journey”.

But there is a lot to be learned at startups, and some people thrive in the sink or swim mentality often present in new companies. Since there is a lot riding on a startup's success, emotions can run high and workloads can be significant. However, that high-stress atmosphere can spawn great creativity, innovation, and reward (RL Priem, 2012). For starting any kind of businesses, it is very much required that how the entrepreneur takes and faces the challenges in front of the world. An entrepreneur is always on the lookout for fresh avenues and the latest technology to stay ahead in the competition. In each of the above steps an entrepreneur must face challenges and the one who is able to cope up with the pressures and uncertainty in the profession emerges victorious. Ideally an entrepreneur is a person with high level of self-motivation and self-initiation, Persistence, patience and skills required to enter into a new venture with the aim of high level of achievement He is the one who either identifies or creates an opportunity for common good and social change and at the same time making economic gains out of it. But in today’s era such skills have become very scarce leading to new type of challenges in entrepreneurship. While starting new business entrepreneurs face so many challenges; such as instability, stress, negative mindset, overwhelming feelings, lack of support, feelings of wanting to give up, growing a business, problems of raw material, problems relating to marketing, outdated technology, lack of infrastructural facilities, lack of skilled labors (RG McGrath,1999). It is important to overcome these challenges to run business effectively. So, to identify the challenges faced by the new entrepreneurs and to analyze the measures to overcome them is the main objective of this study. The success of a Startup company lies in benefiting society. So is for an entrepreneur. To achieve profit new venture creation, this constitutes the core of academic research on entrepreneurship, discussions, and debates over numerous forms of entrepreneurship (Islam, 2011).

This paper focuses on whether the idea of starting a business or becoming an entrepreneur is encouraged or not in a country like India. India is a developing country, and there are many people who are striving to survive. The objective of this research paper is to encourage entrepreneurial development by taking initiatives to beat the challenges obstructing today’s entrepreneurs. To get better clarity about the challenges faced by an entrepreneur and ways to overcome the challenges I interviewed four entrepreneurs. They are Pritam Nanda (EnlveSolutions), Rahul Kanuganti (Flytta Innovations), Badri Narayan Samal (Midday entertainment and media) and Deepak Kumar Nath (GTP).

Significance of Entrepreneurship

Often this the question arises in mind that why some new ventures succeed while others fail? What does entrepreneurship signify, what is its importance in the success of a venture? What types of qualities and skills are favorable for entrepreneurial Success and why so? How should an entrepreneur take decisions? How the success of entrepreneurial activities is influenced by the regulatory, market, and the organizational environment? These above questions which can also be called as challenges of an entrepreneur cannot be answered and no such proper and appropriate theory can be developed because of the interdisciplinary nature of entrepreneurship. A firm’s success completely depends on the entrepreneur. But it is found that with the help of applications of analytics, empirical and experimental tools from a range

of fields, few of the above questions can be answered (Raphael Amit et al, September 1993). Start-ups are growing at a faster rate and social ventures are developing the quality of lifestyle of people. Moreover, it is observed the growth of globalization is resulting in the growth of start-ups. Globalization has created many scopes for startups. It is also determined how exciting opportunities and entrepreneurial activities can be studied to enhance the entrepreneurial activities more world-wide and it is also seen that entrepreneurship is going viral worldwide (Hans N Raw Houser et al, June 2008). Not just the big five personality traits determine the success of an entrepreneur and the firm, it's true that they determine the business intention and success but narrow personality trait like innovativeness or creativity determines the success of an entrepreneur and his firm in a more appropriate manner (Franziska Leutner et al, Jan 2014).

Social Entrepreneurship

Social Entrepreneurship comes with its own challenges and human dynamics. It gives a fresh and new perspective on the term 'entrepreneurship'. Unlike traditional entrepreneurship- where the principal aim is profit-making, social entrepreneurship aims at providing values or enhancing the society at large-often not solely for the purpose of money. It has its own rules and thrives for 'value creation' rather than 'turnover creation' (Filipi M. Santos, 2012). Even advanced researchers have credited social entrepreneurship as mostly non-profit and heavily funded organizations. As a relatively new research stream, there are not enough case studies and citations to back the claims. As is the case in any field of research, social entrepreneurship research needs more example-backed facts and claims. Presently there is a small research base that puts the pros and cons of social entrepreneurship. There are no real steps to success or magic potion that enables successful social entrepreneurship programs. But with more and more people joining the bandwagon it won't take too long when we have a slew of successful social entrepreneurs who will further inspire many more to take up the socially rewarding career. But failure to take this into account and incorporate these nuances into the field of research will only add to the questionable state of legitimacy and academic merit (Jeremy C. Short et al, 2009).

Social entrepreneurship is a scenario and a field for reinvestigation, with an opportunity of challenging, questioning, and rethinking the concepts and assumptions from the various fields of management and business research. This article puts forward a view of social entrepreneurship as a process that protests around social changes and addresses the important social needs regarding the finance for the entrepreneurs. Different researches have different methodologies and their implications are also different (Johanna Mair&Ignasi Marti, 2004).

Importance of Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship is known to be very important as it is looked upon an important source of economic growth, employment, and technological process, in order to understand this in a better way we need to observe entrepreneurship much deeply. Although entrepreneurship involves recognition, innovation, creation of value, exploitation of opportunities entrepreneurship activities is influenced by emotional but still, it is affected by emotional intelligence (GorkanAhmetoglu et al, 2011). An array of studies spread across numerous fields like management, sports psychology, education, counseling psychology, and communication, heap praises on the overall effect of TSL cognitive strategies on cognitions and behaviors. TLS cognitive strategies like mental imagery, thought patterns, beliefs, self-talked train us on constructive management skills like self-leadership and improves performance. However, not many works of literature focused on entrepreneurship development cover this subject. With the proper and diligent application of these principles, practicing and aspiring entrepreneurs can see sustained growth and optimum use of one's potential in the entrepreneurial journey filled with challenges. To sum up the whole article, it is quite clear that the building of an entrepreneur involves the accumulation of required skills, knowledge, experiences, and social/professional network that develops over the number of years and each day in the life of an entrepreneur includes extra-large servings of self-development and hence team development. Granted that an entrepreneur gets to know these learning are over the years of experience by practicing self-leadership-an integral recipe towards entrepreneurial self-development. However such literature and research can help budding entrepreneurs get

that magic formula to succeed in a challenging career filled with magical ups and demotivating downs (Christopher Panicky et al, 2009).

Shortcomings for Entrepreneurial activities

Earlier research on entrepreneurship has shown that the goal, social perception and leadership theories has led to the assumption regarding the relationship between entrepreneurial skills and qualities (passion, persistence and new resources skill) and situational specific skills like the vision, self-efficacy, and goal of venture growth. Structural equation modeling discovered a web of relationships that has influence on venture growth and these factors facilitated the effects of passion, tenacity and new resource skills on succeeding growth. Moreover, communicated vision and self-efficacy were associated with goals and persistence related to new resources to new resource skill (Baum Robert J. & Locke A. Edwin, 2004). Recently the solicitation of thoughts and ideas from knowledgeable has remained increased currency within entrepreneurship exploration, as verified by the growing gathering of positive studies framed in innovative perception terms. Entrepreneurial chances occur, sovereign of the perception of an entrepreneur, just wait for these opportunities formed by the movements of the entrepreneurs. The concepts involve in how the entrepreneurial prospects are formed discovery theory and creation theory is described of the form of the opportunities. An entrepreneur can make the opportunities and involve through the iterative learning process which hints towards the making of the opportunities. The entrepreneur could expend a time to contract with time and energy raising a single, inclusive, and comprehensive business plan. The entrepreneur may discover out that the business design can be written when an opportunity has been created in this process can be at superlative an unwanted of resources and at worst fundamentally deceptive to both entrepreneurs and those that capitalize on them (Sharon A. Alvarez & Jay B. Barey, 2007).

Entrepreneurship involves societal, administrative, and economic variables that change government principles. Entrepreneurial objectives are further organized by together balanced logical thinking areas directed by behavior and visualization. This thought process is the conception of prescribed business plans, opportunity exploration, and other goals focused on the behavior. Bird of entrepreneurship signifying the individual self-efficacy which defines the individual's faith in his or her ability to accomplish an assignment impacts the development of goals and actions of an entrepreneur. This model of entrepreneurship purposely grounded in cognitive psychology that to describe human behavior (Nancy G. Boyd & George S. Vozikis, 1994), an entrepreneur requires a specific definite income that simplifies the appreciation of different prospect and gathering of resources for the venture. Entrepreneurial perception is the widespread practice of an individual heuristics and opinions on the influence of decision making. Where administrative cognition is defined as added organized decision making where executive use accountability and reimbursement schemes. It is more genuine based on the other hand entrepreneurial perception builds from the key experience and beliefs. Entrepreneurs use market systems of governance to coordinate many resources necessary to realize an economic occasion (Sharon, A, Alvarez, & Lowell W. Busenitz, 2001).

Entrepreneur- A risk taker

An entrepreneur has a multidimensional phenomenon. The ideas of risk-taking then its connection with other hypotheses have remained problematic to capture. It's hard to believe that the entrepreneur flashes into taking the improvement of chances that others fail to realize or perform at it. Research on social cognition accepting the new challenges which differentiate the entrepreneur from others while forecasting the changes in risk-taking behavior. An entrepreneur is an individual person who takes judgment and decisions by his own and who innovates the new combination of products in the market with his own risk, entrepreneurship literature revolves around the difference the different predisposition towards risk-taking. The entrepreneurs are the persons who are self-employed, who regulate themselves to the threat in which wherever the return is indefinite. A successful entrepreneur is encouraged by the idea to bring about a confident and well-intended change to the culture. An entrepreneur never gets motivated by the desire to earn money or to earn a few quick

bucks. They are usually highly concentrated personalities who have a crystal perfect vision and they are eager to put all the hard work towards their journey to achievement. An entrepreneur is always on the lookout for fresh avenues and the latest technology to stay ahead in the competition. One of the most challenging jobs of an entrepreneur is to build and maintain a team. However, despite all the hardships, difficulties, and challenges, a successful entrepreneur lives a socially and financially rewarding life. It has its own ups and downs but- if taken on a lighter vein- is like an enjoyable roller coaster ride. Ask any successful entrepreneur and they will say, "It is not easy, but at the end of the day it's worth the efforts". (Leslie E. Palich& D. Ray Bagby, 1995).

CONCLUSION

India is one of the global startup hotspots, but still, a startup is a risky affair in India because of many reasons. 90 percent of startup fail in India because of taking wrong decisions, probably less than 1 percent really achieves their goals in terms of growth, value, and market impact. The first building block of a startup is an idea. Many startups fail because the entrepreneur does not get the right idea, the idea has to be new, innovative, technically sound, socially, and legally acceptable and it should have the potential to make a lot of money. Getting the right idea is very essential, an entrepreneur should know on which idea he has to work. Many startups fails because the entrepreneur gets into the business without analyzing his idea and his ignorance about the external factors affecting his startup. Even people in India don't encourage start-up, they don't believe in risk-taking instead of motivating entrepreneurs they demotivate them.

Startup is a tough nut to crack and the rate of failure is high. An entrepreneur is required to make him ready for facing the failures and hardships. Unfortunately Failure is not taken positively in our culture and is highly unwelcome. So it becomes difficult to innovate as the place where failure is loathed so much, one doesn't dare to even try anything new and different. Idea and its implementation are two different things. Availability of funds on time is another regular problem faced by startups. Banks don't give loans easily to the entrepreneur because of the fear of loss. They feel it is risky to fund a startup. If these all issues were taken care start-ups could be a great success in India. It is obvious that a journey of an entrepreneur is not easy but external support could make it easier for them.

ANNEXURE 1

To get a better clarity about the challenges faced by an entrepreneur and ways to overcome them, we interviewed some entrepreneurs. They are Pretax Nanda (Enlive Solutions), Rahul Kanuganti (Flytta Innovations), Badri Narayan Samal (Midday entertainment and media) and Deepak Kumar Nath(GTP). Below are few mentioned points discussed with them and their views regarding the same.

1. What were some of the biggest lessons that has impacted the way that you work? What was the learning?

Mr. Pritam Nanda, Enlive Solutions: Life of successful entrepreneurs and reading about them have been a great learning experience. No institute teaches you entrepreneurship and hence these valuable resources have been a great help. I closely follow the life of Steve Jobs and Elon Musk. Their lives are a huge motivation and a testament to how motivation and determination can take you to unimaginable heights. The most valuable learning came from the commencement address by Steve Jobs. He said, "Your time is limited, so don't waste it living someone else's life. Don't be trapped by dogma - which is living with the results of other people's thinking. Don't let the noise of others' opinions drown out your own inner voice. And most important, have the courage to follow your heart and intuition."

Mr. Rahul Kanuganti, Flytta Innovations: I started my company in 2015 when the Chennai city flooded, and relocation was a challenge. I got a tremendous amount of learning cannot be defined in one aspect. Start-up is more like a project, an initiative but as we go deep into it there are many things by which business learns. Start-up is an immature business model.

I learned all the business processes. Learned how to set up a business model. Learning is a continuous process and entrepreneurs do not limit themselves.

Mr. Deepak Kumar Nath, Global Tech Promotions: Right from the start, hacking was something that attracted me. I used to be glued to computers and tinkered with software, hardware just to make something that seemed not possible.

Mr. Badri Narayan Samal, Midday Entertainment and Media: My working style has been influenced by consumer behavior in the state of Odisha. Being a company that requires creativity as the lifeblood to survive in the fast-paced and ever-changing advertising industry, every day has been a learning experience.

2. What ignited the spark in you to start a new business venture or to make significant changes in an existing business? How did the idea for your business come about?

Mr. Pritam Nanda, Enlive Solutions: There has been significant growth in computer technology, telecommunications, construction, and in a lot of other fields that we analyze. However, education has been in a sector that has not seen significant growth. I would be wrong if I say that there has been no growth. No. There has been growing but not at a pace as rapid as we will like it to be. I have always believed that education is the root of the economy, employment is the trunk and prosperity (denoted by GDP, affluence, etc) are the fruits and flowers. We give a lot of thoughts to economic prosperity and employment and debate about how they can be improved. However, we neglect the root i.e. education. We believe that if we nurture the roots properly, trunk and fruits will grow by default. By means of graphic-rich content, we make it easier for minds to understand difficult concepts in a way that makes it easy. Rather than blaming students that they are not concentrating and have poor memory, we must understand the functioning of the brain. Brain processes images, videos, and stories better than text. Hence, we remember the movie by seeing it once but cannot remember all that is written in a book even after reading it multiple times.

Mr. Rahul Kanuganti, Flytta Innovations: I took it as a project and over a period thing just moved forward. This project started becoming bigger first we thought to address a hundred people now we want to address thirty-six lakhs people. I believe that solution is an idea. A need which is there and a solution to that is an idea. The best possible way to get out of any problem could be called an idea.

Mr. Deepak Kumar Nath, Global Tech Promotions: I was already quite proficient in methods and tools for hacking. However, I noticed a lot of people were misusing the knowledge to fool people. Therefore, to create sufficient awareness I started GTP. Over the course of time, I realized that it was also a lucrative career option and hence started a training program after partnering with industry stalwarts like Intel.

Mr. Badri Narayan Samal, Midday Entertainment and Media: My working style has been influenced by consumer behavior in the state of Odisha. Being a company that requires creativity as the lifeblood to survive in the fast-paced and ever-changing advertising industry, every day has been a learning experience.

3. How important have good employees been to your success?

Mr. Pritam Nanda, Enlive Solutions: I believe good and bad are both relative terms. To retain a good employee, one must be a good company in his eyes. Entrepreneurship is about trying to be in others' shoes and looking at things from a neutral perspective. Having said that, employees have always played a vital role in achieving whatever success we have

achieved as a young start-up. It is an essential lesson to learn that nothing can be achieved by one person and it takes a team of people as crazy as you about the vision to really succeed.

Mr. Rahul Kanuganti, Flytta Innovations: Success is a parameter which is purely evaluated by the participation of the entire team. Success is not by an individual.

Mr. Deepak Kumar Nath, Global Tech Promotions: In the initial days, I was the sole person who ran the company and is training programs. However, after a certain level, I was stuck in one place and there was no visible growth. Then a mentor advised me about the importance of building a team. Now I understand that my employees are as responsible for the growth of the company as I am.

Mr. Badri Narayan Samal, Midday Entertainment and MediaPriorMedia: Prior to starting Midday, I had over ten years' experience in the field of advertising and event management. But I noticed that there were no one-stop solutions for all needs including advertising, creative printing, event management, etc. This ignited the spark in me to start a company. With good experience and public contacts, I was confident about the idea.

4. If you had the chance to start your career over again, what would you do differently?

Mr. Pritam Nanda, Enlive Solutions: When I started out on the journey, I was all alone and the only thing I carried along with me was my vision of enhancing lives. With the raw youthful zeal, I forgot/or was unaware of certain timeless business lessons and strategies, the importance of advertising and following certain protocols. Now when I am 3 years wiser and look back I see them as clear mistakes and could improve on them. However, these decisions have been critical in building what we are today. So I have no complaints. Entrepreneurship is not a destination it's a journey. So I have really enjoyed the ride.

Mr. Rahul Kanuganti, Flytta Innovations: No, I don't think so, I would have started it in the similar way, I love experimenting and business is something that excites me than day to day job.

Mr. Deepak Kumar Nath, Global Tech Promotions: If I had to start my career all over again, I would choose to be more proactive, more engaged. As I started the company when I was still in college, therefore there was a sense of laid-back attitude. But that has been a learning curve.

Mr. Badri Narayan Samal, Midday Entertainment and Media: If I were to start my career again, I would like to do away with the initial pondering that led to the delay of starting Midday.

5. What would you say are the top three skills needed to be a successful entrepreneur?

Mr. Pritam Nanda, Enlive Solutions: The top 3 skills vital to be a successful entrepreneur are:

- Perseverance and persistence
- Persuasive abilities to woo customers, build a team of winners and retain them.
- Keeping himself and the team motivated even when the chips are down.

Mr. Rahul Kanuganti, Flytta Innovations:

- Time management
- Ability to judge
- Financial management.

Mr. Deepak Kumar Nath, Global Tech Promotions: The top skills of an entrepreneur are networking skills, decisiveness, and a vision for the future.

Mr. Badri Narayan Samal, Midday Entertainment and Media: Three things needed to be an entrepreneurial success is hard work, ethics, and dedication towards all the stake holders.

6. What have been some of your failures, and what have you learned from them? What is your greatest fear, and how do you manage fear?

Mr. Pritam Nanda, Enlive Solutions: Failures are a part of the life of an entrepreneur. Right from the start, I had made up my mind that this is going to be a bumpy ride but there was also a feeling deep down that it's going to be exciting. Along the way, we have seen a lot of failures and each of them has contributed positively towards what we are today.

Mr. Rahul Kanuganti, Flytta Innovations: We faced a major failure when we started, we broke out of funds and I was bankrupt. Not doing something is my greatest fear. I ensure whatever I am doing I tell it my colleagues whom I trust the most in the organization so that they push me hard to make the things done.

Mr. Deepak Kumar Nath, Global Tech Promotions: As an entrepreneur every day brings small failures. It is important to understand that the more you fail, the more you learn. There are occasional butterflies in the stomach when there is an important meeting or deal to be signed. But over the years, I have created a belief that butterflies in the stomach are good. It is a sign that you are progressing.

Mr. Badri Narayan Samal, Midday Entertainment and Media: I was pretty much aware that failures will be a big part of starting an advertising and media company. I have seen days where I have lost clients for a difference of 10 rupees from some other service provider. However, I have always believed in quality and do not shy away from letting some clients go because we at Midday do not compromise on quality.

7. How has being an entrepreneur affected your family life?

Mr. Pritam Nanda, Enlive Solutions: There have been considerable changes in personal life. A lot of adjustments and sacrifices have come along the journey. I am not able to spend the amount of time I used to spend with family. Family life has taken a toll. But these are some adjustments that are a part and parcel of an entrepreneur's life.

Mr. Rahul Kanuganti, Flytta Innovations: My family really supported me; my father did not talk to me for the first 3 months later he supported me because I am good at convincing people. In India, it is a fear, so they support initially.

Mr. Deepak Kumar Nath, Global Tech Promotions: I take time off to spend time with family once every three months during which I spend some quality time. So that is some mild adjustments that I and my family have made.

Mr. Badri Narayan Samal, Midday Entertainment and Media: By the grace of God, I have an incredibly supportive family. Even my daughter who is a school going girl understands certain things about my job. I have numerous time canceled family outings and picnics just for some last moment developments around the business. However, they have been ever supportive.

8. What motivates you?

Mr. Pritam Nanda, Enlive Solutions: The idea of empowering minds with cutting-edge technological innovations and touching lives with knowledge is my biggest motivation. When random people thank us on social media for playing a part in some of his success gives me immense satisfaction and that is exactly what drives our work every morning.

Mr. Rahul Kanuganti, Flytta Innovations: People motivate me as my advisor, mentors, and investors they motivate me and time also motivates me, as time passes you become a better person.

Mr. Deepak Kumar Nath, Global Tech Promotions: The vision of a world free from cybercrime and extortion (through Ransomware) is what motivates me and my team.

Mr. Badri Narayan Samal, Midday Entertainment and Media:I gain motivation from success stories, from failure stories, and from day to day life and events.

9. How do you generate new ideas?

Mr. Pritam Nanda, Enlive Solutions:In a start-up, it's easier to get overwhelmed and busy with a lot of work. However, to think of a new idea one needs a calm head and it's essential to cut-off from the world. I switch off my mobiles and sit down alone and self-reflect on the kind of work we do and what we can do to make it better. Reading books also helps me generate new ideas.

Mr. Deepak Kumar Nath, Global Tech Promotions:We generate ideas from the discussion. It is not just about me. We have monthly discussions where everyone has the liberty to present their ideas. Also talking and meeting like-minded people helps in getting ideas.

Mr. Badri Narayan Samal, Midday Entertainment and Media:Whenever I must think of something, I switch my phones off, sit silently over mugs and mugs of coffee, and come up with something that I feel is a great idea. Until then I shut the door to the world.

10. How do you define success? What is the best way to achieve long-term success?

Mr. Pritam Nanda, Enlive Solutions:For my success is about going to bed with the satisfaction of doing something substantial for the society, for the education community, and waking up every morning with the vision of the start of a day that I will try and make it better than the previous one. The best way to achieve long term success is to do what you believe is great work. Financial success is important but the satisfaction of touching lives with your work is special and gives a feeling way better than monetary gains. Money is just a by-product. (Said by Mr. Pritam Nanda, Enlive Solutions)

Mr. Rahul Kanuganti, Flytta Innovations:Success is the happiness I achieved my 40 percent of my target so I am happy. Success is what you do and if you love doing that you are successful. Consistency can give long term success.

Mr. Deepak Kumar Nath, Global Tech Promotions:Success is not money or fame. It is being satisfied with what you do and chasing a vision. As they say "It is not the destination, it is the journey!"

Mr. Badri Narayan Samal, Midday Entertainment and Media:I see success is being able to be responsible for a large group of people who are my employees and being able to support them and their families in return for the work they do at Midday.

11. What are some of the biggest mistakes you have made?

Mr. Pritam Nanda, Enlive Solutions:In the initial stages one of the mistakes I made was saying yes to all the projects that came along the way. However, soon I realized that your success is as much about what you do as about what you choose not to do.

Mr. Deepak Kumar Nath, Global Tech Promotions:One mistake that I discussed earlier was I understood the importance of team much later. Another mistake I would highlight was in the initial days, I did a lot of things. Any project that came my way, I used to say yes. But eventually, I learned that we can be masters of one and I did not want to be the jack of all trades.

Mr. Badri Narayan Samal, Midday Entertainment and Media:I have made plenty of mistakes and today I can say I am proud of them. Because I am a very analytical person and analyze critically both my failures and success and find ways to make amends in the next possible opportunity.

12. If you were conducting this interview, what question would you ask?

Mr. Pritam Nanda, Enlive Solutions:Have you ever considered the idea of giving up? What kept you going?

Mr. Rahul Kanuganti, Flytta Innovations:I wouldn't have asked any questions because entrepreneurs are of a different mindset if you put them a question you may not get an accurate answer.

Mr. Deepak Kumar Nath, Global Tech Promotions:I am not very good at asking questions. I am not sure if I would add something.

Mr. Badri Narayan Samal, Midday Entertainment and Media:I would ask about the importance of having a co-founder and what are the criteria for choosing the right co-founder.

13. What sacrifices have you had to make to be a successful entrepreneur?

Mr. Pritam Nanda, Enlive Solutions:Some of the sacrifices I have made to pursue my dreams are to let go of the cushions of a corporate job. For a relatively inexperienced person straight out of college, it becomes an additional burden to dodge the society along with the rigors of starting up your own company. I had offers from three of the top-five IT companies in India and to leave all those aside to dive into the unknown has been a great sacrifice when I look back at a 22-year-old self. But God has been kind and I am proud of those sacrifices I made along the way to reach where I am today.

Mr. Rahul Kanuganti, Flytta Innovations:I did not do any sacrifices. I love what I am doing, and sacrifice is the word I don't like.

Mr. Deepak Kumar Nath, Global Tech Promotions:Sacrifices have been all through. I have time and again got health issues, no proper timetables with meals, or sleep. Not being able to spend those weekends with friends and working more than I would have worked on a 9-5 job.

Mr. Badri Narayan Samal, Midday Entertainment and Media:I have been through a lot of struggles to see Midday where it is today. I had to sell off my lands and jewelry to get initial funds to start the business but looking back I would say it was worth it.

14. Excluding yours, what company or business do you admire the most?

Mr. Pritam Nanda, Enlive Solutions:I am always intrigued by the creative innovation and work culture at Apple.

Mr. Rahul Kanuganti, Flytta Innovations:Google, took them a lot of time to make revenues but they have had the vision to serve people and they did it very well.

Mr. Deepak Kumar Nath, Global Tech Promotions:I like Intel as a company for their constant drive to innovate.

Mr. Badri Narayan Samal, Midday Entertainment and Media:I like a lot of modern-day media companies that have come up who have an alternate way to how people consume media. Founded by young people and without an office space. Like the RVCJ or AIB.

15. Where you see yourself and your business in 10 years - 20 years?

Mr. Pritam Nanda, Enlive Solutions:I have always maintained that we want to be the most creatively advanced technology company and the most technologically advanced creative company. Hopefully with the kind of work that we

do, in 10 years, we can reach a stage where we can back our claim. However, we believe in bettering ourselves every day and that will not be a peak we want to reach. We just want to keep climbing and reach as far as we can.

Mr. Rahul Kanuganti, Flytta Innovations:I will be the same person as I am now, I just want to see my organization on a global scale.

Mr. Deepak Kumar Nath, Global Tech Promotions:We see an organization with over 200 employees who provide services across the globe and eradicate the vice of cybercrime and cyberbully.

Mr. Badri Narayan Samal, Midday Entertainment and Media:I see our company shape up into the largest advertising service provider in the state and hopefully in the country.

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